

MNEMONIC FOR ADJECTIVE ENDINGS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE.

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Abstract

Adult learners apply different strategies and techniques to learn the structure of the target language in the foreign country classrooms which lacks the native language atmospheres as well as acquisition period. Russian language is a synthetic language therefore word-endings play vital role in grammatical meanings of the words and sentences. Learning Russian language requires learning how endings change. Endings of the adjectives, possessive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, numerals, and participles in Russian Language is an issue for learners. This research paper presents a keyword mnemonic technique to memorise endings of these grammatical categories.

Keywords: mnemonic, keyword, word-ending.

Introduction: The use of mnemonic dates to 500B.C (Yates, 1966). It is derived from Greek word Mnemosyne which refers to Greek goddess of memory. Earlier form of modern loci was the first used device; since then several mnemonic devices have been developed (Higbee, 1897). Various scholars like Yates's method of loci in 1966 Roediger's pegword method in 1980 and Atkinson's keyword method in 1975 have differently classified mnemonic devices. Mnemonic device is extensively used in analysing and memorising data. Thompson in 1987 has acknowledged the usefulness of mnemonic devices. He advocated that mnemonic device can help learner to link new information with existing information that can provide retrieval clue to recall. It can even minimise the cognitive load to learn new information.

Language is not unidirectional discipline mathematics or physics. It has all verbal or nonverbal signs related subjective or objective existing world. Language holds unstructured data. Therefore, memorizing them needs either implicit learning in natural linguistic environment or explicit learning with proper strategy and mnemonic in artificial foreign language environment.

Russian language is a synthetic language where word-endings play an important role in grammatical meaning. Learning different endings for different associated grammatical meaning of words is important strategy to understand structure of Russian Language. Knowledge of structure of Russian language provide added linguistic ability to synthesise speech. Learning word-endings in Russian language learning is vital for learners. All Russian words have endings; a word can have several endings which play a vital role in formation of grammatical meaning.

Foreign learners lack the native language hence, learners need explicit learning in artificial target language environment like classroom. Classroom learning requires self-sustained motivation and sensorial learning, ambiguity and forgetting linguistic structure with associated grammatical meaning, most of the time, demotivated students and distracts from sensorial learning that decrease foreign language learning.

Current research on mnemonic is focused on mnemonic to propose a keyword technique which links known keyword with series of unknown facts it estimates word-ending of adjectives, possessive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, ordinal numerals participles and conjunction «который». To the author's knowledge, present research on mnemonic to memorise the endings of the said parts of speech in Russian language has been scarcely investigated from the keyword mnemonic point of view.

This research paper on a keyword mnemonic which is to illustrate how to memorise the endings of the adjectives, possessive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, ordinal numerals participles and conjunction «который» is exclusively important for teacher as well as students. Students will easily memorise the endings all these parts of speech of Russian language whereas teacher will use this mnemonic to illustrate word-endings of all above parts of speech easily. Students become active learners using mnemonic clue and cognitive load is decreased which remove boredom in students and promote learning.

Keyword Mnemonic: The Keyword Method is method which is used as key open the unknown facts using known (key) facts by linking with the key. Keyword method functions appropriate when learners learn new information (Scruggs and Mastropieri, 1989). Atkinson in 1975 and Levin in 1981 suggested that keyword mnemonic has two stages: an acoustic link stage and an imagery link stage. Keyword mnemonic is memory aid in which first learners are given a keyword which can be further linked to facts to be learnt (Atkinson R. C., 1975 and

Levin J.R., 1993). Mastropieri and Scruggs in 1989; Bulgren, Schumaker and Deshlerin 1994 have proven that learner can memorise things easily by using mnemonic devices. Therefore, data could be organized and linked into clusters grouping similar concepts and terms together to create keyword mnemonic. Here, declensions of personal pronouns third person singular and plural of Russian Language: «ОН», «ОНА», «ОНО» and «ОНИ» are used as keyword mnemonic for endings.

Case	Singular		Plural
Nominative	он/ оно	она	они
Genitive	<u>его</u>	<u>еѐ</u>	<u>их</u>
Dative	<u>ему</u>	<u>ей</u>	<u>им</u>
Accusative	<u>его</u>	<u>еѐ</u>	<u>их</u>
Instrumental	<u>им</u>	<u>ей</u>	<u>ими</u>
Prepositional	<u>(о) (н)ѐм</u>	<u>(о) (н)ей</u>	<u>(о) (н)их</u>

All oblique case word forms except nominative word-forms of these personal pronouns become the endings of *adjectives, possessive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, ordinal numerals participles and conjunction «который»* accordingly. Nominative forms, that is, «ОН», «ОНА», «ОНО» and «ОНИ» indicate gender and numbers. «Он» indicates masculine gender and singular number. «Она» Feminine gender and singular number. «Оно» indicates neuter gender and singular number. «Они» indicate plural number which lacks the gender identity in Russian language. In Russian language there are two types of consonants soft (palatalized) and hard consonants (non-palatalized) and each word have an ending. Hence, a word can have a soft ending or a hard ending.

We can notice here that all above mentioned word-form starts with palatalized vowel (soft) therefore we need to change that palatalized vowel into non-palatalized (hard) vowel to change them into hard endings. It excludes inanimate feminine accusative endings where «а» changes into «у» and «я» changes into «ю», And no change for inanimate masculine and neuter, here are the endings:

Soft ending	Hard ending	Alternation for hard ending

его, ему, ей and (н)ём etc.	ого, ому, ой and ом etc.	е and ё → о
их, им, ими etc.	ых, ым, ими etc.	и → ы

Now we can summarise the following endings: pair of soft and hard endings:

case	singular			plural
Nom.	он (Hard)	она (Soft/Hard)	оно (Hard)	они (Hard)
Gen.	его (ого)	её (ей/ой)	его (ого)	их (ых)
Dat.	ему (ому)	ей (ей/ой)	ему (ому)	им (ым)
Acc.	его (ого)	её (ей/ой)	его (ого)	их (ых)
Inst.	им (ым)	ей, (ей/ой)	им (ым)	ими (ыми)
Prep.	(о) (н)ём (ом)	(о) (н) ей (ой)	(о) (н)ём (ом)	(о) НИХ (ЫХ)

So, declensions of possessive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, ordinal numerals, adjectives and participles will take the following endings by using this keyword. Further these declensions can be simplified into acronym to memorise all the endings.

Case	singular		plural
Nom.	он/ оно	она	они
Genitive/ Accusative (*).	его(ого)*	ей/ ой	их (ых) (Gen/ Acc./Prep)
Dative	ему (ому)		им (ым)
Instrumental	им(ым)		ими (ыми)
Prepositional	ём (ом)		
егоему-имём (еи - оы)		*ую	ихими (и - ы)

* **Note:** Ending of inanimate feminine accusative «а» changes into «у» and «я» changes into «ю». and no change for inanimate masculine.

Keyword mnemonic: All word-forms of «он», «оно», «она» and «они» (Gen/Acc.-егоему-имём and Gen/Acc./Prep-ихими) would change into endings for adjectives, possessive pronouns,

demonstrative pronouns, ordinal numerals participles and conjunction «который» and some other categories of words.

We can use keyword mnemonic to link the unknown endings.

	Gen	Nom.	Acc.	Gen	Dat.	Pre.	Inst.
Hard	M	ый	* ¹	ого	ому	ом	ым
	F	ая	ую	ой	ой	ой	ой
	N	ое	*	ого	ому	ом	ым
	P	ые	ых	ых	ым	ых	ыми
Soft	M	ий	*	его	ему	ем	им
	F	ья	юю	ей	ей	ей	ей
	N	ее	*	его	ему	ей	им
	P	ие	их	их	им	их	ими

1. Accusative masculine and all genders in Plural - use Genitive if object is human or animal and feminine ending «ая» changes into «ую». Neuter singular does not change.

Adjective Ending:

	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter	Plural
<i>Nominative Case</i>	-ый	-ая	-ое	-ые
<i>Accusative Case</i>	-ый -ых (anim.)	-ую	-ое	-ые -ых (anim.)
<i>Genitive Case</i>	-ого	-ой	-ого	-ых
<i>Dative Case</i>	-ому	-ой	-ому	-ым
<i>Instrumental Case</i>	-ым	-ой	-ым	-ыми
<i>Prepositional Case</i>	-ом	-ой	-ом	-ых

Adjective «новый» ends in the letters -ый which is a hard ending so it will take the hard ending in all its forms.

	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter	Plural
<i>Nominative Case</i>	новый	новая	новое	новые
<i>Accusative Case</i>	новый новых (anim.)	новую	новое	новые новых (anim.)
<i>Genitive Case</i>	нового	новой	нового	новых
<i>Dative Case</i>	новому	новой	новому	новым
<i>Instrumental Case</i>	новым	новой	новым	новыми
<i>Prepositional Case</i>	новом	новой	новом	новых

The soft adjectives simply use the soft form vowel. («ы» becomes «и», «а» becomes «я», «о» becomes «е», «у» becomes «ю»). The word «синий» ends in the letters «-ий» which is a soft ending so it takes a soft ending.

	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter	Plural
<i>Nominative Case</i>	-ий	-яя	-ее	-ие
<i>Accusative Case</i>	-ий -их (anim.)	-юю	-ее	-ие -их (anim.)
<i>Genitive Case</i>	-его	-ей	-его	-их
<i>Dative Case</i>	-ему	-ей	-ему	-им
<i>Instrumental Case</i>	-им	-ей (or -ею)	-им	-ими
<i>Prepositional Case</i>	-ем	-ей	-ем	-их

	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter	Plural
<i>Nominative Case</i>	синий	синяя	синее	синие
<i>Accusative Case</i>	синий синих (anim.)	синюю	синее	синие синих (anim.)
<i>Genitive Case</i>	синего	синей	синего	синих
<i>Dative Case</i>	синему	синей	синему	синим
<i>Instrumental Case</i>	синим	синей	синим	синими
<i>Prepositional Case</i>	синем	синей	синем	синих

Possessive Pronoun endings:

P	G	N	A ¹	G	D	P	I
My	M	мой	мой	моего	моему	моём	моим
	F	моя	мою	моей	моей	моей	моей
	N	моё	моё	моего	моему	моём	моим
Yours	P	мои	мои	моих	моим	моих	моими
	M	твой	твой	твоего	твоему	твоём	твоим
	F	твоя	твою	твоей	твоей	твоей	твоей
	N	твоё	твоё	твоего	твоему	твоём	твоим
	P	твои	твои	твоих	твоим	твоих	твоими

Demonstrative Pronoun endings:

	G	N	A	G	D	P	I
This	M	этот	этот ¹	этого	этому	этом	этим
	F	эта	эту	этой	этой	этой	этой
	N	это	это	этого	этому	этом	этим
	P	эти	эти ¹	этих	этим	этих	этими
That	M	тот	тот ¹	того	тому	том	тем
	F	та	ту	той	той	той	той
	N	то	то	того	тому	том	тем
	P	те	те ¹	тех	тем	тех	теми

1 Accusative Masculine and Plural - use Genitive if object is animate.

Ordinal Numbers

	G	N	A	G	D	P	I
First	M	первый	первый	первый	первый	первый	первый
	F	первая	первая	первая	первая	первая	первая
	N	первое	первое	первое	первое	первое	первое
	P	первые	первые	первые	первые	первые	первые

Endings of «который»

	G	N	A	G	D	P	I
Whi ch/ that	M	ко́торый	ко́торый	ко́торого	ко́торому	ко́тором	ко́торым
	F	ко́торый	ко́торый	ко́торого	ко́торому	ко́тором	ко́торым
	N	ко́торый	ко́торый	ко́торого	ко́торому	ко́тором	ко́торым
	P	ко́торый	ко́торый	ко́торого	ко́торому	ко́тором	ко́торым

Conclusion: Keyword is an effective technique for Russian language as foreign language learning where there is structure and systems linked together. It has word-endings which are vital grammatical concepts. Students needs to learn and understand the concepts to understand the structure of the Russian Language. This keyword mnemonic can be used to learn the endings of adjectives, possessive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns, ordinal numerals participles and conjunction «который» and some other categories of words in all the cases.

Mnemonic promotes structuralism, cognitivism, and connectionism theory of learning by developing self-sustained motivation to establish the active sensorial learning in the learners. It removes ambiguity and boredom in the learner by decreasing he cognitive load by channelizing and developing spiral connections between the chunk of grammatical categories. This keyword mnemonic can be used in instructional methodologies in the classroom to make students active learners. This mnemonic can help learners to develop such own keyword mnemonic to learn linguist data and meaning.

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